

A Study of Ion-dipole Interaction Energy of Some Common and Tetraalkylammonium Ions in Different Solvents

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Ion-dipole interaction energy, ΔE_{ID} , of some cations and anions in five solvents namely H_2O , DMA, DMSO, EC and PC** and dipole-dipole interaction energy, ΔE_{DD} , of these five solvents have been calculated. The ratio $\Delta E_{ID}/\Delta E_{DD}$ has also been calculated for the R_4N^+ ions in these solvents. The calculated values of ion-dipole interaction energy have been found to be exceptionally high for the common and compact cations like Li^+ , Na^+ , etc. and appreciably high for the anions like F^- , Cl^- , Br^- etc., whereas in case of tetraalkylammonium ions (R_4N^+), these values have been found to be quite low but slightly greater than the corresponding dipolar interaction energy of the solvents except in H_2O for larger R_4N^+ ions. The dipole-dipole interaction energy value decreases with increasing size of the solvent molecule. The ratio $\Delta E_{ID}/\Delta E_{DD}$ has been found to be greater than unity in all cases except for larger R_4N^+ ions in water which appear to be solvated, specially the smaller ones in EC, PC, DMSO and DMA; however in case of water only $(CH_3)_4N^+$ and $(C_2H_5)_4N^+$ ions are supposed to be solvated. Solvation of ion has been found to be directly related to the dielectric constant of the medium.

MANY approaches like electrolytic conductance¹⁻⁴, apparent and partial molal volumes⁵⁻⁹, activity coefficients¹⁰⁻¹², viscosity¹³⁻¹⁵ etc., have been utilised to study ion-solvent dipole interaction of various common cations, anions and symmetrical tetraalkylammonium ions in aqueous and some non-aqueous solutions. However, some abnormalities particularly in case of R_4N^+ ions have been reported perhaps due to their large size and symmetrical nature. Devanathan and Fernando¹⁰ from e. m. f. measurements showed that in aqueous solutions, R_4N^+ ions have abnormal activity coefficients ranging from 1-14 at ordinary concentrations. Kay and his associates^{2,14} from conductance and viscosity measurements concluded that Me_4N^+ ion is a structure breaker; the larger R_4N^+ ions promote the structure of water while the behaviour of Et_4N^+ is midway between the two extremes. Gopal and Singh⁹ reported that alkali metal ions like Li^+ , Na^+ , K^+ etc. appear to be more solvated than R_4N^+ ions both in aqueous and non-aqueous solutions. Padova and Abrahamer⁶ from the partial molal volume measurements of some R_4NBr salts in methyl alcohol pointed out that Br^- is solvated by only one methanol molecule.

Some attempts have been made to explain the above mentioned interesting results on the basis of ion-solvent interaction but no definite general conclusion can be drawn so far. Thus it appears interesting to arrive at the general mechanism of ion-solvent interaction in different solvents.

In the present communication, an attempt has been made to study the abnormal behaviour of common ions

in general and that of symmetrical R_4N^+ ions in particular from the point of view of ion-dipole interaction energy data in different solvents.

Calculation and procedure: From the dipole moment of solvent and radius of the ions and solvent molecule, ion-dipole interaction energy, ΔE_{ID} , and dipole-dipole interaction energy, ΔE_{DD} , have been calculated using the relations namely¹⁶

$$\Delta E_{ID} = -\frac{e\mu}{\gamma^2} \quad (i)$$

$$\Delta E_{DD} = -\frac{2\mu^2}{\gamma^3} \quad (ii)$$

Where μ is the dipole moment of solvent molecule, e represents the charge on the ion (usually taken as 4.8×10^{-10} esu) and γ the distance between the centres of an ion and a solvent molecule or between two solvent molecules.

The values of ΔE_{DD} of five solvents namely H_2O , DMA, DMSO, EC and PC together with their dipole moments and the Van der waals' radii are given in Table 1. Whereas Table 2 reports the estimated value of ΔE_{ID} of some common cations, anions and symmetrical tetraalkylammonium ions in the above said solvents along with their crystallographic radii as reported by Pauling¹⁷ or Robinson and Stokes¹⁸. Table 3 lists the ratio of ion-dipole interaction energy and dipole-dipole interaction energy i. e., $\Delta E_{ID}/\Delta E_{DD}$ for R_4N^+ ions in the five solvents taken for this investigation.

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** DMA=Dimethylacetamide; DMSO=Dimethylsulfoxide, EC=Ethylene carbonate; PC=Propylene carbonate.

TABLE 1—DIPOLE-DIPOLE INTERACTION ENERGY, DIPOLE MOMENT AND VAN DER WAALS' RADII OF DIFFERENT SOLVENTS

Solvent	Van der Waals' radius in Å	Dipole moment $\mu \times 10^{18}$	Dipole-dipole interaction energy $\Delta E_{DD} = -2\mu^2/\gamma^3$ KT
H ₂ O	1.45 ^b	1.85 ^b	6.82
EC	2.87	4.87 ^d	6.09
PC	3.11	4.94 ^e	4.93
DMSO	3.15	3.95	3.73
DMA	3.22	3.80	2.62

(a) Van der Waals' radii of EC, PC, DMSO and DMA molecules have been calculated by using their molar volumes due to unavailability of these data in the literature; (b) R. W. Gurney, *Ionic Processes in Solution*, McGraw Hill Book Co. Inc., New York, 1953, p. 50; (c) S. J. Bass, W. I. Natham, R. M. Meighan and R. H. Cole, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1964, 68, 503, 509, (d) R. F. Kampa and W. H. Lee, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 1, 100, (e) L. Simieral and R. L. Amey, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1970, 74, 1443.

Results and Discussion

Effect of size of the solvent molecule on solvation of ions: From Table 1, it is clear that dipole-dipole interaction energy decreases as the size of the solvent molecule goes on increasing i. e., order of the ΔE_{DD} is H₂O > EC > PC > DMSO > DMA. Therefore, DMA molecule with lowest dipole-dipole interaction energy can be disrupted easily in comparison to the water molecule with highest dipole-dipole interaction energy. Thus smaller the radius of the solvent molecule, lesser will be the solvation of an ion in contact with solvent molecules.

From Table 2, it may be noted that for smaller common ions like Li⁺, Na⁺, K⁺ etc., ion-dipole interaction energy is about 4-12 times more than the respective dipole-dipole interaction energy. For the larger common ions like Rb⁺, Cs⁺, F⁻, Cl⁻ etc., ion-dipole interaction energy is about 2-4 times more than the corresponding dipolar interaction energy of the solvents. Almost similar results are reported¹⁹ in some other nonaqueous solutions.

TABLE 2—ION-DIPOLE INTERACTION ENERGY OF SOME ALKALI METAL CATIONS, HALIDE IONS AND TETRAALKYLAMMONIUM IONS IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS

Ion	Crystallographic radius in Å	H ₂ O	Ion-dipole interaction energy, $\Delta E_{ID} = -e\mu/\gamma^2$			KT DMA
			EC	PC	DMSO	
Li ⁺	0.60	51.28	47.14	41.80	36.71	30.38
Na ⁺	0.95	37.40	38.88	34.72	30.09	25.50
K ⁺	1.33	27.94	32.07	29.15	25.26	21.37
Rb ⁺	1.48	25.02	29.89	27.24	23.55	20.04
Cs ⁺	1.69	21.87	27.20	24.79	21.48	18.37
NH ₄ ⁺	1.42	26.00	30.87	27.94	24.21	20.59
F ⁻	1.36	27.24	31.56	28.64	24.79	21.13
Cl ⁻	1.81	20.07	25.72	23.78	20.39	17.50
Br ⁻	1.95	18.64	24.29	22.34	19.42	16.54
I ⁻	2.16	16.55	22.42	20.70	17.71	15.31
No ₃ ⁻	2.03	17.79	23.62	21.76	18.64	16.06
OH ⁻	1.76	20.95	26.47	24.28	20.82	17.87
Me ₄ N ⁺	3.47	8.91	14.13	13.27	11.22	9.88
Et ₄ N ⁺	4.00	7.24	12.02	11.36	9.57	8.50
Pr ₄ N ⁺	4.52	6.04	10.39	9.88	8.28	7.39
Bu ₄ N ⁺	4.94	5.27	9.30	8.87	7.42	6.65
Pen ₄ N ⁺	5.29	4.71	8.52	8.16	6.80	6.10
Hex ₄ N ⁺	5.59	4.34	7.90	7.59	6.30	5.71
Hep ₄ N ⁺	5.88	4.00	7.39	7.12	5.80	5.34

TABLE 3— $\Delta E_{ID} / \Delta E_{DD}$ VALUES FOR R₄N⁺ IONS IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS

Ion	Radius (Å)	H ₂ O	EC	PC	DMSO	DMA
Me ₄ N ⁺	3.47	1.30	2.31	2.69	3.00	3.77
Et ₄ N ⁺	4.00	1.06	1.97	2.30	2.56	3.24
Pr ₄ N ⁺	4.52	0.88	1.70	2.00	2.21	2.82
Bu ₄ N ⁺	4.94	0.77	1.52	1.79	1.99	2.54
Pen ₄ N ⁺	5.29	0.69	1.40	1.65	1.82	2.36
Hex ₄ N ⁺	5.59	0.63	1.30	1.54	1.69	2.18
Hep ₄ N ⁺	5.88	0.58	1.21	1.44	1.55	2.04

In the case of R_4N^+ ions, as clear from the Table 2, ion-dipole interaction energy is generally higher than the dipole-dipole interaction energy of the solvent except in water, in which ion-dipole interaction energy is smaller than the dipolar interaction energy specially for larger ions like Pr_4N^+ , Bu_4N^+ , Pen_4N^+ etc., which, therefore, may be regarded as unsolvated in water. This may be a reason for the abnormal behaviour of R_4N^+ ions specially of larger ones in water.

Thus ion-dipole interaction energy as well as dipole-dipole interaction energy both play equal important roles in the solvation of ions and in deciding net structure breaking or promoting effects in case of different ions. In order to have a more clear picture of R_4N^+ - solvent interaction and to see the effect of various factors on the solvation of ions in different solvents, it seems desirable to calculate the ratio of ion-dipole interaction & dipole-dipole interaction energy for different R_4N^+ ions. These values, given in Table 3 are plotted against crystallographic radius of R_4N^+ ions in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Plot of $\frac{\Delta E_{ID}}{\Delta E_{DD}}$ vs. γ (the crystal radius in Å units) for some R_4N^+ ions in some solvents.

From Fig. 1, it is clear that in all the solvents, all the points lie on a straight line except those corresponding to Me_4N^+ and Et_4N^+ ions, indicating some special type of ion-solvent interaction in case of Me_4N^+ and Et_4N^+ ions. For larger R_4N^+ ions, although the ratio, $\Delta E_{ID}/\Delta E_{DD}$ decreases linearly with the increase in the size of the ion but the ratio is always greater than unity for the ions considered here (except in case of water in which it is less than unity). The linear decrease of the ratio $\Delta E_{ID}/\Delta E_{DD}$ indicates the decrease in the extent of solvation with the increase in the size of the ion. On extrapolating these straight lines towards radius axis, it is possible to obtain the limiting radius of the ion of a particular series of which ion-dipole interaction energy is zero ($\Delta E_{ID} \rightarrow 0$) i. e., solvation is nil and ion will not be a structure breaker. In case when the value of ratio $\frac{\Delta E_{ID}}{\Delta E_{DD}}$ is less than one, as is the case with larger R_4N^+ ions in water, the ion may be structure breaker or may not have any effect. The ion may be structure promoter if value of ratio $\frac{\Delta E_{ID}}{\Delta E_{DD}} \geq 1$. These values of limiting radius of the ion for which $\Delta E_{ID} \rightarrow 0$ thus obtained are given in Table 4.

TABLE 4—LIMITING VALUES OF THE RADIUS WHEN $\Delta E_{ID} \rightarrow 0$

Solvent	Dielectric constant (ϵ) at 25°	Lim $\Delta E_{ID} \rightarrow 0$ γ (ion) in Å
H ₂ O	79.7	8.50
EC	95.3	9.20
PC	64.72	9.45
DMSO	46.6	9.65
DMA	37.78	9.80

Fig. 2. Plot of $\lim \frac{\Delta E_{ID}}{\Delta E_{DD}}$ (ion) vs ϵ (Dielectric constant of the solvent) for some solvents.

An interesting finding of this investigation is that the plot of limiting values of the radius for different solvents taken here against the dielectric constant of these solvents, is a straight line as shown in Fig. 2. From Fig. 2, it is clear that the points correspond to four solvents namely DMA, DMSO, EC and PC lie on the straight line while the point corresponds to water which lie much below the straight line. This may be justified by pointing out that water has hydrogen bond interaction in addition to dipole-dipole interaction while DMA, DMSO, EC and PC are non hydrogen bonded. The straight line nature also gives a convincing information that the ion-dipole interaction i. e., solvation of the ion seems to depend upon the dielectric constant of the medium which has already been pointed out from apparent molal volume studies²⁰⁻²².

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